

PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET

DISSIDENT TRANSTEXTUALITIES

CERES NGO

BASE INFORMATION

OFICIAL NUMNER	:	669047
NAME	:	Dissident Transtextualities
COUNTRY	:	Chile, Región Metropolitana, Ciudad de Santiago
FUND AND LINE	:	Fondo de Cultura Fondo del Libro y la Lectura Fomento de la Lectura y/o Escritura Iniciativas de fomento lector y/o escritor en medios de comunicación. Convocatoria 2023
PROJECT OFFICER	:	Non-Governmental Development Organization Centro de Estudios de la Realidad Social — ONG CERES (Center for Social Reality Studies — CERES NGO)
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SPONSORING INSTITUTION	:	Ministerio de las Culturas, las Artes y el Patrimonio de Chile (Ministry of Cultures, Arts and Heritage of Chile)
AMOUNT ASSIGNED	:	CPL 28.459.042
IMPLEMENTATION TEAM	:	Débora Oníria de Erehwon Fernández Cárcamo Kevin Andre Magne Tapia Ignacio Alonso Yáñez Castillo María Jesús Ibáñez Canelo

DESCRIPTION

Dissident Transtextualities is a project with a gender equality and human rights perspective, whose purpose is to promote awareness and cultural integration, development, and diversification of transaffirmative and gender-inclusive themes in the Chilean social and cultural field. Its design arises from the experience of research, social advocacy, and content production of the Gender and Trans-Subjectivities Area of the NGO CERES. By promoting the visibility of sex-dissident works, we sought to promote the understanding of literary production processes, connecting them with critical aspects such as the configuration of identity phenomena, the vindication of social rights, and the challenges experienced by trans* and sex-dissident communities, as reported in national and international human rights.

VISUAL IDENTITY

Transtextualidades *Disidentes*

PERIOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

The project was developed, as planned in its initial development plan, between March 1, 2023 and February 29, 2024. The temporal order of the phases is as follows:

Phase I	Research	12 weeks: March, April and May
Phase II	Pre-productio	4 weeks: June
Phase III	Production	8 weeks: July and August
Phase IV	Post-production	8 weeks: September and October
Phase V	Diffusion	12 weeks: November, December and January

AUTHORS AND WORKS

Authors	Book title	Year of publication	Description
Gabriel Inti	Desgenerada. Antología de mi ser	2018	Erotic poetry
Shane Cienfuegos	A través del CISTema. Memorias de una travesti chica	2020	Autobiographical poetry
Juan Pablo Sutherland	Nación Marica. Prácticas culturales y crítica activista latinoamericana.	2021	Compilation of writings and archival images
Constanza Valdés	¿Un cuerpo equivocado? Identidad de género, derechos y caminos de transición.	2021	Autobiographical essay with images
Leufü Manke	El río que llevo adentro Ti leufü ñi yeniel ponwi mew.	2021	Mapuche poetry
Rudy Pradenas y Cheril Linett	Anarcografías del cuerpo. Performances de Cheril Linett (2015 - 2021).	2021	Catalog of artistic works and compilation of essays
Débora Oníria de Erewhon y Rita Lages	Actas del Primer Ciclo de Simposias «Nuevas cuerpas para nuevas transformaciones».	2021	Digital compilation of academic and activist interventions
Lilith Kraushaar	Tú no sabes si vas a volver.	2024	Archival catalog with essays

SET OF SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW QUESTIONS IMPLEMENTED DURING PHASE 1

1. How would you define the book's approach in terms of narrative, composition, visuals, or advocacy?
2. Let's talk about desire and the social imaginary related to its origin. How did the book come into being? What motivated it? What literary or cultural references influenced it? Which projects or authors were on your mind while writing it?
3. How would you describe the role of gender and sexual identity in the book?
4. What were your expectations regarding the publication of your book?
5. Here, I will present specific questions focusing on the book's content and uniqueness, developed based on my reading and its materiality.
6. How would you describe the current social recognition of trans* or sexually dissident literature in the country?
7. What do you think are its greatest challenges?
8. What has been your experience with the circulation of your book?
9. What criteria and strategies did you consider when shaping the impact your book will leave?
10. Considering that this interview will result in a script that will serve as the foundation for creating an audiovisual capsule, what else would you highlight about your book's approach?

PRODUCT

- [Almacenamiento website](#)
- [Versión subtitulada al Inglés](#)
- [Versión inclusiva, con lenguaje de señas y audiodescripción](#)

PRODUCTION PARTNERS

- CINESPECIE, in charge of visual production and post-production.
- Almada Media, responsible for the creation of accessibility and sign language translation tools.

DIFFUSION

The project achieved national and regional media coverage, such as publications in digital media such as El Mostrador and Gran Valparaíso, as well as press releases in media collaborating with the project, such as Ruidosa, Closet Magazine and the Feminist Observatory of Books and Reading. In addition, new creative networks were generated, arising from the interaction between Transtextualidades Disidentes and the following media: Conecta.te, Centro Cultural España, La Biblioteca Cuir and OTD Chile. The main promotional channel was the Instagram of ONG CERES. Below are the posts generated by the authors inviting you to watch the webseries:

- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C0mXIYauxxu/>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C1ATpDJuMqy/>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C1nHFarOhik/>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C1Uv5qkuIJ0/>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C12DrohOvWx/>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C2IC36bODYn/>

- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C2aCMPquusT/>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/C2sGZATur5R/>

CREDITS

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- Audiovisual Direction: Kevin Magne [@kevin.magne](#)
- Script: Ignacio Yáñez [@ignacioyanezcastillo](#) y Andrea Arizmendi [@andrea.m.ac](#)
- Audiovisual Production: CINESPECIE [@cinespecie](#)
- General Production and Edition: Nico Videla
- Director of Sound: Andre Millán
- Director of photography: Inti Lorca [@le.dualite](#)
- Director of Art: Eduardo Cerón [@eduardoceron](#)
- Graphic design: Bastián Pérez Streuly [@bstnprz](#)
- Music design and production: Manuel Araya [@m4anu](#) .
- Color postproduction: [@albatros.post](#)
- English translation: Gabriel Larenas
- Makeup: Yatra [@yatra_vulcania](#)
- Accessibility tools: Almada Media [@almadamedia.cl](#)
- Diffusion coordination: María Jesús Ibáñez [@todasabailar](#)
- Territorial location: Municipalidad de Recoleta [@municipalidadrecoleta](#)

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